

Strategic implication of the global mobile phone industry: Analyzing COVID-19 impact from competitive viewpoint

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to analyze the present pandemic impact for Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) on global mobile phone industry specifically focusing on smartphone demand and sales in context of strategy implementation. Here the author tries to show the competitive scenarios of global mobile phone companies in current situation. This study is based upon a systematic literature review and analysis of published secondary data. The global mobile phone brands were progressing aggressively overtime especially for smartphones. A sudden unexpected situation that is known as global pandemic declared by WHO about a century later in the history of human civilization stops this progress and makes companies bound to go backward. The findings of this study suggests that there is significant negative impact of COVID-19 on global mobile phone brands primarily especially in the big markets of this industry likely China, India, USA, Europe but later on it can be seen some positive impact on the industry too especially in some developing countries. The positivity of this industry is due to the expanded demand for the mobile phone as some sectors like education shifted online which triggered up the need for purchasing new smart devices like laptop, smartphone, tab etc. The outcome of this study is useful for the industry policy maker, investor, user, and other stakeholders of global mobile phone industry to understand and tackle present and future COVID-19 situation. Finally, some strategic approaches are discussed and appropriate solutions are suggested to cope up with the pandemic situation and attain success.

Keywords: COVID-19 impact; competitive approach; five forces model; global brand; mobile phone industry; strategic implication

1. Introduction

Mobile phone industry emerges in the marketplace on a sudden and got fastest growths besides the internet (Chan et al., 2006). It does not have a long historical background. According to Wikipedia (2018), mobile phone comes into existence by Motorola researcher and executive United States of America (USA) citizen Martin Cooper on April 3, 1973. After that, mobile phone devices get global acceptance. Likewise, different national and multi-national companies start producing commercial mobile phone. In the same year, Motorola's chief of portable communication products and Cooper's boss, played a key role in advancing the development of handheld mobile telephone equipment. Then, Mitchell successfully pushes Motorola to develop wireless communication products that would be small enough to use anywhere and thus participates in the design of the cellular phone. Thus Motorola, Inc. is the first multi-national company that is established in September 25, 1928, based in Schaumburg, Illinois. But this pioneering company is not in existence today.

Strategic implication of the global mobile phone industry: Analyzing COVID-19 impact from competitive viewpoint

It has stopped its business operations since 2012. It is sold to Google in 2012, and later on acquired by Lenovo in 2014. The historical evolution of mobile phone and wireless communication is shown in the following table:

Figure 1: Historical perspective of wireless telecommunications

Source: The Internet

A mobile phone referred to as also cell phone is a mobile electronic hand-held device that is mainly used for distance communications having some bundle of features. The features may include voice call, video call, short messaging service, internet browsing and surfing capabilities, global positioning system, multimedia services (audio-video), camera and so forth. The mobile phone industry has passed the growth stage of industry life cycle and exists in the maturity stage. So, the market is much more competitive than earlier ('Persistence Market Research', 2018). The global mobile phone companies face difficulties from the regional mobile phone producers. Mobile phone giant NOKIA's global sales have drastically fallen down and it is facing the challenge existence.

Strategy is a very old concept. It is a military term. Chinese military general and philosopher Sun Tzu (545 BC-470 BC) wrote a book named "The Art of War". Military people used this term to defeat enemies in the war and win the war. Likewise, business people started use this term in business to outcompete rivals and to achieve success in their business. Hill et al. (2015) define strategy as a course of actions used to outcompete rivals. These actions include attract and please

customers, compete successfully, conduct operations efficiently and achieve targeted levels of performance. Strategic management is the strategic decisions of strategic leaders to formulate and implement strategies. Hill and Jones (2007) mention that competitive advantage is a firm's ability to outperform its competitors (earn higher profits). The source of competitive advantage is value creation for customers. Sustained competitive advantage comes from maintaining higher profits than competitors over long periods of time. Pon et al. (2014) conduct a comparative case study in the smartphone industry to analyze platform strategies and suggest that operating system has aborted to be a bottleneck or control point. Again, operating systems are contributing to enhance the popularity of mobile phone brands. Different operating systems are being used in smartphone like Android, iPhone OS, BlackBerry OS, Symbian and Windows etc. All of this operating system is not similarly popular throughout the world. For example, Blackberry is popular in North America whereas iPhone operating system has recently witnessed a high growth rate in North America ('Persistence Market Research', 2018). These smartphone companies have been depending on the cloud based services to create value and lock-in users (Pon et al., 2014).

COVID-19 has originated and been found from Wuhan, China on 31st December 2019. It has spread approximately 216 countries around the world that is still ongoing (Usman et al., 2020; WHO, 2020). WHO (2020) reports in their website that there are 20.16 million confirmed infected cases where 0.74 million death cases globally. Among the infected countries, nearly 52% are from top 3 countries USA, Brazil and India. Again, around 42% have died from these three countries out of total deaths throughout the world. Other countries having high death rates are in Mexico, UK, Italy, France, Spain, and Peru having higher than 20K measures. Worldwide, medicine specialists are struggling to invent vaccine to prevent this virus from almost the beginning of the pandemic situation but no success stories have not been heard. Kamal et al. (2020) and UN News (2020) report that this virus will not disappear rather sustain for long lasting as announced by WHO. Fortunately, the good news is on 11th August, Russian president Vladimir Putin declared that his country approved a vaccine against corona virus. Although, there are controversy with this vaccine of its quick launch (The New York Times, 2020), this initiative must show smiles to billions of people all over the world and will work as motivation for other specialists to bring more effective vaccines in future. To encapsulate the overall scenario and impact of COVID-19 in global economy specifically on global mobile phone industry and to discuss the strategic implications arising from this pandemic, there is necessity of conducting a thorough study.

It can be inferred that the pandemic situation has positive impact as it has increased demand for global smartphone brands because of the urgent need for distance learning, work from home, and increased communication with dear ones due to lockdown. On the other hand, it can also be inferred that it has negative impact as it reduces purchasing power of customers due to income loss, joblessness, economic activity shutdown. Thus the research question would be what are the actual impacts of COVID-19 on global mobile smartphone brands? What strategic approach should these companies take during and after the pandemic situation?

Based on the assumptions and research question, the primary purpose of this study is to show the impact of COVID-19 and analyze the strategic implications of global mobile phone industry. The specific purpose is to discuss the:

Strategic implication of the global mobile phone industry: Analyzing COVID-19 impact from competitive viewpoint

- The major global mobile phone brands based on industry position
- Global mobile phone industry market analysis and competitive scenario
- Major changes occurred in the industry due to COVID-19
- Major trends and consequences of the rise of this industry
- Future strategic options of the industry for achieving success

This study includes mobile phone industry throughout the world. It includes ins and outs of the industry in the perspective of strategy implementation in and out COVID-19 pandemic situation. Thus the study might be useful to the industry specific companies, research scholars, market analysts and other related stakeholders.

The study is constructed on a systematic way. The whole study is divided into 7 parts including introduction where historical overview of global mobile phone industry is shown and an overview of COVID-19 has given. Then, literature from previously conducted articles has been studied. Next, the methodology of the study has been discussed. After that, an overview of global mobile phone industry where global mobile phone brands, products, competitive forces and generic strategies have been discussed as well as future strategic options chronologically and finally conclusion and future research direction are given.

2. Review of literature

Cecere et al. (2015) discuss the smartphone's evolution from vertical and horizontal innovations perspectives and mention that day by day new smartphones are increasing due to entrance of new companies. They find a fierce competition in horizontal innovations although perceived nearly same in vertical innovations and conclude with no dominant design has been identified yet in this industry. Campbell-Kelly et al. (2015) study on the evolution of smartphone industry from multi-sided platform theory that analyzes various strategies which is useful to solve chicken-and-egg problem for mobile operating systems at the starting point. This theory based on survey evidence also examines the approaches that is used by mobile platforms to continue momentum with users. This continuance of users' momentum is required to involve various user groups. Likewise, they analyze the way of mobile platforms to interact with network carriers, advertisers, and third-party app developers. Finally, they provide an explanation of Apple's and Google's relative success. Park and Koo (2016) analyze smartphone market's operating system switching costs using hierarchical Bayesian multinomial logit model. Their finding is positive that is USD 171 but this cost relies on consumer characteristics. Shin (2015) uses a customer satisfaction index (CSI) model for smartphones and finds that perceived value and satisfaction are significant variables as well as there are heuristic implication for effective policies and competitive strategies. Other researchers Galetovic et al. (2018) find that mobile phone technologies are developed and licensed by specialized companies and estimates an average cumulative royalty yield in mobile phone value chain which was USD 7.20 per phone (3.3%) in 2016. They claim that decentralization produces high royalties.

Rennhoff and Routon (2016) estimate telephone services demand in USA where they find a monthly consumer surplus of USD 35.5 which is aggregately USD 7.03 billion from inception of smartphone. Smartphone is the stronger substitute for landline than featured phone. Thus they suggest that smartphone growth triggered down the growth of landlines. Funk (2009) studies on Japanese mobile phone industry to show how this industry is changing to a value network from value chain.

He shows that many interface standards are creating relationship between mobile phone and other industries. He finds that the change to a value network needs a different form of standard setting, policy making, and management than are used presently in mobile phone industry. Narayana (2011) studies on Indian public and private sectors growth contributions in telecom services using the framework of a Logit model and estimates that demand for socio-economic determinants of this services are fixed. The result shows a strong negative effect in price and a positive effect in income variables. It makes distinction in necessity of social caste, nature of occupation, level of education, family size, and age of household head between mobile and fixed phones that provide evidence for mobile phones substitutability for fixed phone. Ward (2014) finds a considerable impact of mobile phone use on economic growth of China whereas smaller impacts from fixed line use. This effect is high when it was less developed country. They develop an estimation strategy to lower the possible endogeneity bias.

Carton et al. (2018) studies on smartphone usage pattern and future forecast and finds that every fifth person will possess a smartphone globally. This forecasting is based on the unbelievable demand for smartphone making it a new global tech cycle. Mongardini and Radzikowski (2020) study that global smart phone mobile sales may be peaked. They mention that in 2016 with around 1.5 billion units sold, global smartphones fell down in 2019 with around 1.4 billion units sold indicating that the market has been saturated. In Canalys (2020) reports, it is mentioned that in second quarter of 2020, smartphone shipments fell down 14% globally where china's smartphone market reduced by 7%, a slight improvement than first quarter. In their further study, they show there will be negative growth of global smartphones brands in near future at least for 5 years. This negativity will be happened due to low penetration of users in market and high replacement cycle. But the entrance of 5G may open up a new industry picture with increased trend of customer demand and as a result positive sales growth.

Staboulis and Lazaridou (2020) mention that it is common that pandemic situation occurs in the history of human civilization. Usman et al. (2020) conduct a detailed study on economic impact of COVID-19. Again, many other researchers have already worked and have been working on the impact of COVID-19 from economic perspective. The study of VoxEU (2020) specifies that just before pandemic situation, the global economy was rosy, tension free and cheerful which situation has changed due to COVID-19. It brings about most sufferings to the economic sector all over the world. It is contagious to economy as like medical sector. Where European Union (EU) said Italy and France are at risk to go into economic recession on 4 March 2020, International Monetary Fund said there is extreme chance for fall of global economy. Borri (2020) mentions that the economic impact of COVID-19 is acute where Fernandes (2020) comment that global recession is almost inevitable. Nicolaa et al. (2020) and VoxEU (2020) identify that it has triggered up the probability of unwanted economic crisis and recession and again, production of commodity and manufacturing products have decreased. In other words, this sector suffers from triple hit for disruption of direct supply, supply chain contagion and disruption of demand. According to VoxEU, "COVID-19 will worsen the global manufacturing downturn" (2020). Nicolaa et al. (2020) specify that multinational companies and distributors will manufacture and source beyond China over years. Baker et al. (2020) mention no infectious disease in the past like Spanish Flu was as devastating as like COVID-19 that affects stock market severely. Study of Czech et

Strategic implication of the global mobile phone industry: Analyzing COVID-19 impact from competitive viewpoint

al., (2020) identifies continuous pandemic results in depreciation of Visegrad currencies. Waheed et al. (2020) mention that due to COVID-19, stock markets of developed countries go to an uncontrolled situation (Onali, 2020) where in developing countries like Pakistan has a positive increase in stock returns that is the result of in time response from government. Elleby et al. (2020) specify that due to income loss and supply chain disruption (Fernandes, 2020), pandemic leads to people in developing countries suffer from food insecurity although global food consumption is not so much affected. Saha and Khan (2020) conduct a survey and find that people whose regular activity are affected their financial crisis becomes high during lockdown, mental health becomes poor especially for female.

After COVID-19 appears, primarily, few countries pursue a laissez-faire approach and lately almost all governments emphasize on restrictive controls ("COVID-19 will reverse economic gains in the Caribbean," 2020). Bartik et al. (2020) and Vidaurreta et al. (2020) study on its effect on small business and found these businesses are severely affected where many are closed down and most of the remaining are at risk. Cowling et al. (2020) find that during pandemic time, 39% SME businesses have been strengthening cash balances where 61% might run out of cash involving 8.6% had no retained earnings mentioning that micro business companies are at risk. Kabir et al. (2020) argue that pandemic situation will have long lasting impact in health hazard, financial difficulty, and future employment opportunity of garment workers in Bangladesh. These issues should be considered by stakeholders e.g., international buyers, BGMEA, govt. and policymakers. Another study argues that due to coronavirus, the economy of Spain is affected badly and comments that an immediate recovery of the economy is not possible ("Spain's economic recovery from COVID-19 will be slow, 2020)

Radanliev et al. (2020) study global pandemic management based on comprehensive bibliographic review and propose solutions to pandemic management predictive, preventive and personalized way based on social machines and connected devices. McMaster et al. (2020) say that COVID-19 has affected supply and demand negatively and indicate a need for building flexibility to lessen risk of epidemic and demand. Narang et al. (2020) reveal that some companies are more capable of resilience than others and mostly affected companies are small in size, low profitable and loser found from univariate analysis. Goyal (2020) and Haubrich (2020) mention that it is important to enhance macroeconomic stimulus and attain financial stability to recover and sustain after COVID-19 pandemic situation. McKibbin and Fernando (2020) recommend that financial institutions should ensure that affected economies carry on functioning while pandemic sustains.

Kamdi and Deogade (2020) study a completely different impact of COVID-19 showing the positive impact. They identify that due to lockdown, there are few vehicles in road which in turn produce lower air and water pollution, road traffic accidents, as well as low crime rate. It facilitates people spending quality time with family members, fulfill hobbies, learn many new skills, understand importance of sanitation, hand hygiene, and social distancing. They conclude with remark that it also reminds us the need for an improved healthcare system and clinical studies as well as the need for improving immunity. This situation shows a short term emission of greenhouse gas though having no long term effect. Another study of He and Harris (2020) argues that it opens up extended opportunity for businesses to play corporate social responsibility to mitigate global social and environmental crisis.

They also discuss on how pandemic situation has changed the marketing concept, context and strategies due to COVID-19. Yoo and Managi (2020) calculate COVID-19 global mortality benefits using the age- and country-specific value of a statistical life (VSL) and identify that accumulating actions of using the age- and country-specific value of a statistical life (VSL), social distancing, home quarantine, school closures, and case isolation may save up nearly USD 40.76 trillion globally where social distancing accounts for 55% of benefits and mention USA, Japan, and China may get most benefits.

Kaur et al. (2020) mention that COVID-19 has brought about change in the way of doing business. Businesses have pursued innovative way to achieve success. It has boomed e-commerce businesses, video conferencing platforms, education technology vendors. It is also making a truly digital world as a concept of new normal. Kaushik (2020) specifies that COVID-19 brings about paradigm shifts in workplace and businesses need to cope up with this change otherwise there will be survival question. Radanliev et al. (2020) mention that instead of having and deploying available digital methods for slowing down or clogging COVID-19 and upcoming pandemics, the globe is not prepared and no lessons have been learned from earlier pandemic cases. Budd et al. (2020) study on digital technologies in response to COVID-19 and mention that the quick response enhances use of mobile phones, huge online datasets, connected devices, minimum cost computing resources, as well as development of machine learning and natural language. Oliver et al. (2020) say that mobile data is used to deduce human movement and social interaction. A TV news performed by Sarowar (2020) reports on 14th August that in Bangladesh, people's dependency on technology has increased due to COVID-19 though it has confined their lives because they are dependent on online platform to remove their stagnation to bring normality in schooling, shopping even in treatment. As a result, although COVID-19 has reduced the ability to buy despite enhanced the demand of laptop, mobile phone and online gadgets. As mobile phone is cheaper than laptop that can fulfill the demand of attending online class, doing shopping and conducting office work, people's interests are drawn on purchasing it. This demand is increased as markets start to open from 10 May partially and almost fully after Eid-UI-Adha and people start purchasing new mobile.

By this time, many research activities have been conducted throughout the world. Venkatesh (2020) studies on COVID-19 on scientific research. He mentions that there is a moral significance for science to assist people fight this tough time and finally recover and sets an agenda for research. He categorizes the agenda into three distinct areas and provides direction to study on (i) jobs - job loss, job changes, job outcomes, coping, and support, (ii) home life - home life changes, children, life-related outcomes, social life, and support, (iii) Overarching possible research directions and considerations- social life, support focal groups, general issues and special considerations. According to Research Gate (2020) repository, there are 82,204 in total published and working papers categorized into many disciplines including meta-analyses (1677), machine learning and deep learning (1289), mobility and location data (427), transmission routes (753), epidemiological surveillance reports (26), epidemiological models (1885), control and exit strategies (8998), SARS (5929), MERS (854), protecting frontline workers (3805), psychological impact (1796), social and economic impact (4028), case reports (491), medical imaging (1008), mortality and progression risk factors (5133), laboratory screening (1997), clinical pathology (1864), candidate treatments and therapies (4501), In-silico drug

Strategic implication of the global mobile phone industry: Analyzing COVID-19 impact from competitive viewpoint

screening and development (723), virology and immunology (1903), pathogenesis (3355), vaccine design (2235). This statistics is drawn till 14th August which number may increase many-folds in future. We can see a considerable number of articles published on the discipline of social and economic impact. The current study responds to Venkatesh's (2020) possible research direction and considerations of changes to social life, support to cope with demand, and role of technology as well as Research Gate's (2020) repository categorization of social and economic impact. The author finds few related economic impact articles of COVID-19. Most of the common literature related to this discipline is shown in the following table systematically from where it is evidently found an unexplored area of global mobile phone industry which has implication in social and economic impact that requires a new study:

Table 1: Systematic analysis of literature on impact of COVID-19

SN	Author and year	Method	Author country	Studied country	Field of COVID-19 impact	Key Finding
1	Usman et al. (2020)	Literature review	Pakistan and Malaysia	Worldwide	Global macro economy	COVID-19 seriously affects global economies because of labor immobility, productivity deduction, irregular supply chain, exports collapse, uncertainty, and so forth
2	Nicolaa et al. (2020)	Literature review	United Kingdom (UK)	Worldwide	Socio-economic implication	Medical and food sectors have been facilitating significantly enhanced demand
3	Borri (2020)	Case study	Italy	Italy	European Financial Markets	Policy makers need to consider the Italian experience to see the cost-benefit analysis effectiveness of various policies
4	Bartik et al. (2020)	Survey	USA	USA	Small businesses	Many small businesses have shut down, are financially flimsy, seek coronavirus relief fund for continuity
5	Vidaurreta et al. (2020)	Data analysis using SPSS 24.0	Spain	Spain	Spanish small ruminant's flocks	Short-term negative economic impact

Strategic implication of the global mobile phone industry: Analyzing COVID-19 impact from competitive viewpoint

SN	Author and year	Method	Author country	Studied country	Field of COVID-19 impact	Key Finding
6	VoxEU (2020)	Mixed methods as it is compiled from many chapters	UK	Worldwide	E Global macro economy	<p>Debate regarding effect of COVID-19 becomes more serious in global pandemic</p> <p>Companies sourcing input from China reducing production</p> <p>Contraction of global economic activity due to restriction in transport facility</p> <p>Market behaves anomaly for distortion in usual consumption pattern of consumers due to panic</p> <p>Global financial markets have plunged</p> <p>Effect is almost as hard and sharp as global economic recession in 2008-2009 and would more lengthy than that collapse</p> <p>More permanent damage may occur in global trade system</p> <p>USA' continuous war with partnering countries e.g., China may repatriate their supply chains</p> <p>More intensive use of ICT in supply chain would be useful for global sourcing coordination</p>
7	Kabir et al. (2020)	Personal conversation	Australia and Bangladesh	Bangladesh	Ready made garment workers	Impacts garment workers' health as a result losing their job
8	Kaushik (2020)	Book chapter	India	Worldwide	Implications in human life and	Impacts human life and business organization as a game changer and challenges employers

SN	Author and year	Method	Author country	Studied country	Field of COVID-19 impact	Key Finding
					business	
9	Prohorovs (2020)	Forbes Magazine article	Latvia	Worldwide	Public debt and economic recovery	Countries that will increase in public debt for economic recovery after pandemic will in reverse decrease level of macroeconomic stability Countries that have the ability to decrease public debt in the situation of economic growth will allow them to increase level of macroeconomic stability and international competitiveness
10	Narang et al. (2020)	Event study methodology using sample of Standard & Poor's (S&P) Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) 500 companies	India	India	Stock market response	Initially suffers from a significant stock market downfall but gets rebounded after a setback Surprisingly stock market fall down happens when there was small confirmed cases and no lockdown where recovery occurs when there are huge cases and during lockdown The variation in stock market reaction is due to firm-specific characteristics
11	Elleby et al. (2020)	Global multi-commodity agricultural market model	Spain and France	Worldwide	Global agricultural markets	COVID-19 causes huge decline in global economy and consequently international meat prices decline to 7-18%, dairy product by 4-7%, biofuel product strongly compared to normal situation
12	Czech et al. (2020)	TGARCH model	Poland and Czech Republic	Visegrad Group	Financial markets	TGARCH model reveals a positive significant correlation between the number of reported COVID-19 cases and the exchange rates and there is a negative significant link between the Visegrad group countries' (Czechia, Hungary, Poland, and Slovakia) stock market indices and spread of COVID-19.

Strategic implication of the global mobile phone industry: Analyzing COVID-19 impact from competitive viewpoint

SN	Author and year	Method	Author country	Studied country	Field of COVID-19 impact	Key Finding
13	McKibbin and Fernando (2020)	Global hybrid Dynamic Stochastic General Equilibrium/ Computable General Equilibrium (DSGE/CGE) model	Australia	Worldwide	Global macro economy	Demonstrate a significant short term negative impact on global economy Find that the cost of disease can amplify quickly
14	Fernandes (2020)	Data analysis for financial forecasting	Spain	Worldwide	Global macro economy	There will be atypical impact across sectors Some economy will be more affected than other e.g., more service-oriented economy will be more vulnerable On an average, the expected GDP growth for world economy in 2020 is -2.5% if shutdown continue for 1.5 months and -6.3% if it is 3 months again -10.4% when 4.5 months Mortality rates and economic impact are not correlated
15	Staboulis and Lazaridou (2020)	Trend analysis	Greece	Worldwide	Economy, Employment and New Skills	Overall affected sectors have reduced output ranging from 30-40% Overall GDP has decreased by 20-25% in major advanced economies and the actual impact depends on duration of lockdown Consumer spending has reduced in the field of clothing, footwear, package holidays, car purchase, hairdressing, recreational services, restaurants and household furnishings ranging from 50-100% Public and private sector companies, educational institutions have been forced to implement digital transformation in areas

SN	Author and year	Method	Author country	Studied country	Field of COVID-19 impact	Key Finding
						of telecommunication, on-demand food and services, virtual events and the use of the cloud as many jobs have shifted to work from home A number of new skills are emerged e.g., ability to adopt self-isolation, transparency of work, empathy, trust in people, collaboration, self-management skills, social intelligence skills and innovation skills, creativity, personal skills, lifelong learning
16	Sumner et al. (2020)	Calculate impact using international poverty lines	UK	Worldwide	Monetary poverty	COVID-19 poses actual challenge to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UN SDG) of ending poverty by 2030 as it could increase for first time after 1990 which number can increase by 420–580 million
17	Guerrieri et al. (2020)	Keynesian supply shocks	USA	Worldwide	Macroeconomic implications	A 50% shocks hit all sectors and 100% shocks hit half the economy Business shutdown and job loss enhance initial effect, increasing the recession
18	Cheng et al. (2020)	Empirical analyses based on Longitudinal Current Population Survey (CPS)	USA and China	USA	Labor market activity	Reopening generates reemployment opportunity having low job loss rate People reemployed will return to their previous employer but in a decreasing rate with time since loss of job People groups with highest unemployment rate in April will get lowest reemployment rate resulting in harmful churn with more and longer job losses
19	Bartik et al. (2020)	Survey methods using Current Employment	USA	USA	Stock market	Unhealthy companies are more likely to close and less likely to reopen and at the same time, disadvantaged workers are more likely to be sacked off and less likely to return. These sacked off workers may be recalled and it is predicted to

Strategic implication of the global mobile phone industry: Analyzing COVID-19 impact from competitive viewpoint

SN	Author and year	Method	Author country	Studied country	Field of COVID-19 impact	Key Finding
		Statistics (CES) of employers, Current Population Survey (CPS), a monthly survey of about 60,000 households, and matching interviews with them				rehire
20	Baker et al. (2020)	Text-based methods	USA	USA	Labor market	Suggest that shutdown of business activity, social distance, high dependency on service-oriented economy act as the prime cause of stock market of USA devastation than the earlier epidemic in 1918-19, 1957-58 and 1968
21	Abu-Rayash and Dincer (2020)	Model for smart transportation	Canada	Belgium, Singapore, Sweden, France, Russia, and Hong Kong	Aviation and travel	Canadian Civil aviation activities dropped by 71% Cities with higher than 50% mobility index include Brussels, Singapore, Stockholm, Lyon, Paris, Moscow, and Hong Kong with the highest mobility index of 76% American cities have the lowest mobility indexes lower than 20% Whereas Canadians economy and businesses shut until situation becomes normal Chinese, Russians, Indians, and Italians find it vital to restart the economy
22	Topcu and	Quantitative analysis by	Turkey	Argentina, Brazil,	Emerging	Negative impact of pandemic on emerging stock markets has gradually fallen and begun to taper off by mid-April

SN	Author and year	Method	Author country	Studied country	Field of COVID-19 impact	Key Finding
	Gulal (2020)	estimation of coefficients by a pooled Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression method		Chile, China, Colombia, Czech Republic, Egypt, Greece, Hungary, India, Indonesia, Korea, Malaysia, Mexico, Pakistan, Peru, Philippines, Poland, Qatar, Russia, Saudi Arabia, South Africa, Taiwan, Thailand, Turkey and United	stock markets	Impact of the outbreak has been the highest in Asian emerging markets Impact on European stock markets is lowest

Strategic implication of the global mobile phone industry: Analyzing COVID-19 impact from competitive viewpoint

SN	Author and year	Method	Author country	Studied country	Field of COVID-19 impact	Key Finding
				Arab Emirates		
23	Hao et al. (2020)	exploratory study	Hong Kong	China	Hotel Industry	Propose a COVID-19 management framework that addresses the anti-pandemic phases, principles, and strategies and four Post-COVID-19 strategies including multi-business and multi-channels, product design and investment preference, digital and intelligent transformation, and market reshuffle.
24	Gujrati and Uygun (2020)	Review	Turkey	Worldwide	Global economy	Due to lock down, all sorts of work has been closed and fall slowdown likely schools, colleges, theatre, mall, picnic point, restaurant, hotel, tourism, transportation, railway, seaport, airport, industries, manufacturing companies
25	Mogaji (2020)	Survey using convenience sampling technique	UK and Nigeria	Nigeria	Transportation	The lockdown and restrictions on movement found ineffective in emerging economies result in higher transportation costs, lower transportation mode and traffic affect economic, religious, and social activities Develops 'avoid-shift-improve' framework which is useful for policy makers in both public and private field
26	Sigala (2020)	Literature review	Australia	Worldwide	Tourism research	COVID-19 creates a transformational opportunity for tourism industry

3. Method

To validate assumptions, and to answer the research questions, it is required to study existing literature in details. Thus, the study is based on data of existing literature on COVID-19 impact and global mobile phone industry that is a hot topic in current situation in every sector. The sources of data include various books, journal articles, annual reports, conference papers, websites, newspapers, web logs, reports, working papers collected from internet. These data are collected by using appropriate search words like COVID-19 impact, global mobile phone, economic impact of COVID-19, strategic implications, from world’s prominent academic publishers’ database e.g., Elsevier, Springer, IEEE, Emerald, Google scholar, Research gate, and Google chrome search engine. This is an exploratory study that uses mixed approach using both qualitative and quantitative data. To discuss and analyze the quantitative data, time series data are collected from renowned websites of global mobile phone brands like Huawei, Samsung, Apple, Xiaomi, Oppo, Vivo, Realme, Lenovo, LG, ZTE annual reports; third party analysts company like Canalys, Counterpoint, International Data Corporation (IDC), Gartner, Statcounter, Statista etc.

4. Overview of global mobile phone industry

A group of companies offering products or services that are close substitutes for each other and that satisfy the same basic customer needs is called an industry (Wikipedia, 2018). A global industry is a number of companies operating their businesses’ functional activities worldwide beyond national boundaries. A company operating under this industry is called a global company. The following table shows the features that form global business and the relative difference from other type of businesses:

Table 2: Dimensions upon which global business differ from other types of international business

Criteria	1st Stage	2nd Stage	3rd Stage	4th Stage
Type of Business	Domestic	International	Multinational	Global
Focus	Domestic Market	similarities in the foreign markets	Differences in foreign markets	Reality / similarities Unifying influences and differences in world markets
Orientation	Domestic	Ethnocentric	Polycentric	Geographic
Strategy	Domestic	International	Multi-domestic	Global
Structure	Domestic	International Division	For products or by areas	Matrix
Marketing Strategy	Domestic	Extension	Adaptation	Extension Adaptation Creation

4.1. Major global mobile phone companies

The Motorola Company is the first global mobile phone company in the world. Afterwards, different companies started their mobile phone business worldwide. There are huge numbers of mobile phone companies in the world. Most of the companies operate their business in more than a single country. And some are globally recognized companies. Among all famous global mobile phone brands, top eleven are tabulated below with some of their particulars:

Table 3: List of top 11 global mobile phone brands

S N	Global Brand Name (origin name)	Founder	Eestablishment	Headquarter	Year of released
1	Samsung	Lee Byung-chul	1938	Seoul, South Korea	1988
2	Huawei (Huawei Technologies Co.)	Ren Zhengfei	1987	Shenzhen, China	1997
3	iPhone (Apple Inc.)	Steve Jobs Steve Wozniak Ronald Wayne	1976	California, USA	2007
4	Xiaomi (Xiaomi Inc.)	Lei Jun	2010	Beijing, China	2011
5	OPPO (Oppo Electronics Corporation)	Chen Mingyong	2001	Dongguan, China	2004
6	Vivo (Vivo Communication Technology Co)	Shen Wei	2009	Dongguan, China	2009
7	Realme	Sky Li	2018	Shenzhen , China	2018
8	LG (LG Corporation)	Koo In-hwoi	1958-1995 (Lucky-Gold Star), 1995 (renamed LG-Life's Good)	Seoul, South Korea	1995
9	Lenovo (Lenovo Group Ltd)	Liu Chuanzhi	1984	Beijing, China	2012
10	ZTE (ZTE Corporation)	Hou Weigui	1985	Shenzhen, China	2002
11	Alcatel-Lucent (TCL Communication Technology Holdings Limited)	Li Dongsheng	1981 (TTK), (2006 merged in Alcatel-Lucent enterprise, 2016	(i) Shenzhen, China (ii)Boulogne-Billancourt, France (iii) Espoo, Finland	2004

SN	Global Brand Name (origin name)	Founder	Eestablishment	Headquarter	Year of released
			acquired by NOKIA)		

Source: Internet

4.2. Products and markets of key global mobile phone companies

Each of the mobile phone producer designs, develops and markets a number of models time to time. The demand for mobile is the most variable one. That's why a model may exist in the market only for 6 months or even less. As stated above, mobile phone industry has an immense number of companies worldwide; some of the 11 top listed companies' number of markets served, latest top sold products and units sold per year are shown in the following table:

Table 4: Products and markets of top 11 global mobile phone brands

SN	Global Brand Name	Brand Logo	Markets Served	Top products	Units shipped/year (in million)
1	Samsung		79	Samsung Galaxy S7 edge+, Galaxy Note 7, Galaxy J7 Prime 2, Galaxy S9, Galaxy S8	315
2	Huawei		170	HUAWEI Mate RS, HUAWEI P20 Pro,	152
3	iPhone		40	iPhone 6s, iPhone 7, iPhone 8, iPhone 8 Plus	215
4	Xiaomi		20	Redmi, Mi series Mi MIX 2S, MIUI 9	95
5	OPPO		31	Find 5, 7, N1, N3, A77	111
6	Vivo		100	X series, V series, Y series X20 UD, V9 mobile series	95
7	Realme		27	Realme 5i, 5, 5 Pro, C2, 3, U1	35
8	LG		118	G-Series, K-Series, LG Tribute, LG G Flex, LG Nexus	55
9	Lenovo		160	P Series, K Series, Zuk Series, A Series and VIBE Moto Z, ZUK Z1	50

Strategic implication of the global mobile phone industry: Analyzing COVID-19 impact from competitive viewpoint

SN	Global Brand Name	Brand Logo	Markets Served	Top products	Units shipped/year (in million)
10	ZTE		160	ZTE Axon M	45
11	Alcatel-Lucent		170	Flash-OneTouch series A50, A30 plus, Idol 5S, Pop 4 plus	20

Source: Internet

5. Discussion on COVID-19 impact on mobile phone industry

Generally, mobile phone companies produce smartphone and featured phone. The global mobile phone industry has an increased sales growth. Although in 2017, worldwide smartphone declined 0.5% for the first time year-over-year (Y-o-Y). International Data Corporation (IDC) forecasted that mobile phone companies may enjoy a 2.8% Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) from 2017 to 2022 with 1.68 billion sales volumes in 2022 (IDC, 2018). But this CAGR assumption may not be proved correct and the reason for this variation is for COVID-19. Framingham (2020) reports that global mobile phone industry suffers a Y-o-Y decline in sales in first quarter of 2020. John (2020) reports that global smartphone vendors see further fall in smartphone sales worldwide inevitably. He mentions global smartphone recorded worst performance in second quarter of 2020 with 16% fall Y-o-Y. In this quarter, Huawei outperforms Samsung for first time with 55.8 million units shipment compared to 53.7 million units of Samsung's shipment and Oppo outperforms Vivo thus confirmed fifth position in global mobile phone industry. In 2017, the total delivery of smartphone devices was 1.46 billion units. Egham (2020) writes "Gartner says global smartphone sales declined 20% in first quarter of 2020 due to covid-19 impact". The following table shows the scenario of global smartphone shipments.

Figure 2: Quarter wise growth of global smartphone shipments

Source: Canalys (2020); IDC (2020)

Framingham (2020) reports that during first quarter of 2020 global mobile phone brands shipped 275.8 million units smartphone with highest decline ever over the last three years. China experienced the highest decline from regional stand point that covers almost a quarter of global shipments. Next, USA and Western Europe also experience drastically decline with around 16% and 18% respectively. The below mentioned table and figure show the world’s 5 topmost global mobile phone companies’ Y-o-Y smartphone shipment and market share with growth rate.

Table 5: Some top smartphone companies’ worldwide shipments, market share, and Year-Over-Year growth, Q1 2020 (shipments in millions of units)

Company	Shipment Volume (million)		Market Share (%)		Shipment Volume (million)		Year-Over-Year Change (%)	
	1Q20	2Q20	1Q20	2Q20	1Q19	2Q19	1Q20	2Q20
1. Huawei	49.0	55.8	17.8	18.7	59.1	58.7	-17.1	-5
2. Samsung	58.3	53.7	21.1	23.2	72.0	76.3	-18.9	-30
3. iPhone	40.0	45.1	13.3	10.8	42.0	36.0	-0.4	25
4. Xiaomi	29.7	28.8	10.7	9.7	27.8	32.1	6.1	-10
5. Oppo	22.3	25.8	-	9.2	25.7	30.6	-	-16
6. Vivo	21.6	-	9.0	-	23.9	27.0	7.0	-
Others	73.8	75.5	28.1	29.4	89.7	71.1	-17.2	-23
Total	295.3	284.7	100.0	100.0	334.2	331.8	-13.2	-14

Source: Counterpoint (2020); Canalys (2020), Smartphone Analysis (2020); IDC (2020); Gartner (2020)

Singh (2020) reports referring Canalys research report that the world’s second largest smartphone market India is tremendously affected by COVID-19 falling its sales by 48% in second quarter of 2020 in comparison with likely quarter of previous year. In this market, nearly 17.5 million units of smartphone shipped down from 33 million in that quarter in 2020 and 2019 respectively where 33.5 million was in first quarter in 2020. In the first quarter, the world’s largest market of this industry, China experienced an 18% drop of shipments when this country was in mostly affected zone. But at that period, India was not mostly affected and their shipments grew by 4%. In this quarter, global shipments is reduced by around 13%. In contrary, Canalys (2020) reports that India experiences a 48% decline that is 50.6% according to John (2020) in global smartphone growth with 17.3 million units shipment and in contrary 18.4 million compared to 36.8 million units in previous year. Xiaomi, India’s largest smartphone vendor since 2018 shipped largest quantity in second quarter declaring around 29.4% market share (John, 2020). The second dominant company, Samsung which was mostly dominated brands in India’ market once occupies 26.3% market share although they have 48.5% year-over-year decline. Vivo captures around 21.5% market share with 3.7 million unit shipment in the same quarter.

Strategic implication of the global mobile phone industry: Analyzing COVID-19 impact from competitive viewpoint

Subsequently, Realme and Oppo place fourth and fifth positions. To recoup the loss, most of the brands introduced new models in the country. Along with coronavirus, other factors also work as obstacles for the industry's some of the participants like anti-China sentiment like Boycott China drastically reducing shipments. These smartphone companies e.g., Xiaomi, Vivo, Oppo etc. might avoid backlash as other atypical companies like Samsung, Nokia, Apple are very much price competitive. Apple's iPhone that covers only 1% share in India's market that is still dominating the premium segment of smartphone market was not so affected with fall of 20% in shipment Y-o-Y. A general comparative table is shown below:

Figure 3: Smartphone shipment estimates for the Indian market through Q2 2017 to Q2 2020

Source: Canalys (2020); Singh (2020)

Egham (2020), reporter of Gartner reports that people stop buying nonessential products at the first spike of COVID-19 and decline consumer spending because of global shelter-in-place. Apple was affected by closing their factories in China temporarily resulting in supply constraints and negative sales growth of 41 million units (8.2%). iPhone starts global momentum at the eve of 2020 introducing new product line as well as online channel that help the company reach record level in the quarter. While worldwide smartphone vendors suffer 14% decline in shipment in 2020 second quarter that is 16% according to John (2020), iPhone enjoys 25% growth compared to the same quarter of previous year when they shipped 45.1 million units compared to the total global shipment of 285 million units. Apple's iPhone 11 continues best seller at nearly 40% of their total sales volume. Huawei, world's second (first in Q2 2020) largest smartphone company's sales decline to 42.5 million units (27.3% Y-o-Y decline) in first quarter of 2020 even with 14.2% market share. It has launched Huawei Mobile Service (HMS) ecosystem but it can't create new buyers in global market having lack of Google apps and Google play

store. Oppo faces 19.1% decline in smartphone sales but its online channel will strengthen its sales online.

Samsung News Room (2020) publishes the world's largest global mobile phone brand Samsung's second quarter results where they mention that mobile phone profitability remains solid with increased shipments among market competition in third quarter of 2019. The IT and mobile communications division earned 18 billion consolidated revenue and 1.7 billion operating profit in this quarter. The demand for mobile phone in North American, European and in global market decreases quarter-over-quarter amid lockdown situation despite reduced marketing costs and offline promotions and efficient cost management make it possible of solid profits. It suffers from 28.9% decline in global shipment YoY in second quarter (John, 2020). Hence, this company expects to achieve increased smartphone sales anchored by strong product mix introducing flagship, galaxy note, and foldable phone models (Egham, 2020). Although uncertainty persists, from next quarter overall market will recover gradually by timely responding to demand in various regions through promoting flagship and strengthening market lineup amid COVID-19. Instead of delayed deployment of 5G services due to coronavirus pandemic globally, Samsung explores for business growth opportunity. How this issue can affect this industry, a simple analysis is shown in the following table:

Table 6: Market analysis based on annual sales revenue and profits of top listed global mobile phone companies based on pandemic situation

S N	Global Brand Name	Yearly Units Sold (Smartphone units in million)								Yearly sales revenue (USD in million)		Yearly net income (USD in million)		Market Share (%)		
		2018 Q1	2018 Q4	2019 Q1	2019 Q2	2019 Q3	2019 Q4	2020 Q1	2020 Q2	2018	2019	2018	2019	April 2018	October 2019	July 2020
1	Huawei	39.3	59.7	59.1	56.6	66.8	56.2	49.0	55.8	105,191	123,640	8,543	9,030	6.21	10.02	20.00
2	Samsung	78.2	69.8	72.0	76.3	78.2	70.4	58.6	54.2	209,163	197,690	38,049	18,652	30.76	31.49	19.50
3	iPhone	52.2	65.9	42.0	36.5	44.8	72.3	40.0	37.6	265,595	260,174	59,531	55,256	19.23	22.09	13.50
4	Xiaomi	28.1	25.6	27.8	32.3	31.7	32.9	29.7	28.5	25,182	29,634	1,940	1,454	6.12	7.79	10.20
5	Oppo	24.2	31.3	25.7	30.6	32.3	31.4	22.3	24.0	60,000	60,000	1,400	1,400	3.97	4.10	8.60
6	Vivo	18.9	26.5	23.9	27.0	31.3	31.5	21.6		46,484	46,484	1,125	1,125	7.81	8.00	7.00
7	Realme	-	-	2.8	5.0	10.2	7.8	7.2		-	-	-	-	0.00	2.00	2.00
8	LG	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		51,730	52,540	1,240	150	3.22	2.40	2.03
9	Lenovo	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		51,038	50,716	842	998	2.53	0.96	0.74
10	ZTE	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		12,311	13,063	1000	831	0.63	-	-
11	Alcatel-Lucent	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		553	779	38	-29	0.47	-	-
12	Others	121.8	115.8	87.7	92.8	84.7	98.6	66.6	78.4		-		-	19.05	10.97	16.43

Source: “Apple annual report” (2020); Canalys (2020; Counterpoint (2020); “Huawei annual report,” (2019); IDC (2020); “Lenovo annual report”, (2020); “LG annual report” (2019); MBA Skool Team (2020); “Samsung annual report”, (2020); Statcounter (n.d.); Statista, (n.d.); “Xiomi annual report” (2020); “ZTE annual report” (2019)

The above table shows that more than 80% in 2018, around 90% in 2019, and around 84% in 2020 global market share is occupied by top 11 global mobile phone brands. Huawei ranks top in second quarter of 2020 with 20% market share and Samsung second having market share of 19.5% (John, 2020). Other popular brands having market share of 1.3% by Alcatel-Lucent, 2.68% by Motorola, 1.73% by Nokia, 1.15% by Sony Ericsson, 1.29% by BBK, 0.97% by HTC, 1.06% by Micromax, 1.09% by Asus, 1.96% by Mobicel, 0.28% by General Mobile, 0.44% by Google Pixels, 0.41% by Sony and so forth (Statista, n.d.). From the table, we can guess that between 2019 and 2020 there are some differences of performance among top giant mobile phone companies. Especially major differences are seen in between second quarter of 2019 and first and second quarters of 2020 in terms of units sold as a result it affects the revenue and profit earnings. As we know COVID-19 first infect in the end of last quarter of 2019 and spread worldwide quickly, the major differences are seen afterwards. This scenario illustrates the negative impact of COVID-19 on mobile phone companies. Although the real impact can be measured after the pandemic situation overcomes and the in-depth analysis will be conducted based on time series of data. But we can say that this effect is not as alarming in comparison with other industries as we see surrounding us many industries are badly affected due to COVID-19 such as manufacturing sector like ready-made garments, footwear, apparel, jewelry, accessories etc.; service sector like education, restaurant, tourism, transport especially civil aviation (Abu-Rayash & Dincer, 2020), film and media etc.; bureaucratic relationship like export-import, expatriate where we can see some sectors like technology, treatment, medicine, e-learning, social media, working at home have been increased.

As COVID-19 has an adverse impact on physical classroom, educationalists explored and found alternative way of delivering lectures through online. In this perspective, the enhanced demand for smart phone devices has increased many-fold among students and teachers of all level e.g., universities and colleges (Truong, 2014). "Mobile learning (m-learning) is the study and practice of using mobile devices, such as smart phones, mobile phones, tablets, PDAs, MP3s and pocket PCs in learning and teaching" (Oyelere, Suhonen, & Sutinen, 2016, p. 35). It allows students anytime anywhere learning opportunities without limitations (Oyelere, Suhonen, & Sutinen, 2016). M-learning applications are effective tool of learning and living in preschool education. According to GSM communications, "Handheld mobile technologies are emerging in classrooms, as they seem to support children with special need while they increase motivation to learn, improve fluency skills, encourage collaboration, and improve reading comprehension" (Drigas & Kokkalia, 2016, p. 63). These applications are also recognized by students as fulfillment of their educational requirements (Dirin & Nieminen, 2015). Karabatzaki et al. (2018) mentioned that "with recent advances in the capabilities of smart mobile devices and their growing penetration rate among the student cohort, it is possible to take advantage of these devices to design appropriate exercises and tools that foster student's knowledge and learning" (p. 142). The study of Rojas-Osorio & Alvarez-Risco (2019) finds that students continuance intention of using smatphone of Peruvian university is influenced significantly by perceived ease of use (PEOU), perceived usefulness (PU) and attitude toward to keep using a smartphone. A study of Alwraikat & Al Tokhaim (2014) reveals that the faculty members' attitudes of King Saud University in Saudi Arabia for mobile learning is positive. Polyakova (2020) states "industry 4.0 needs now or will need in the immediate future Education 4.0" (p.

5) and this concept is “now more relevant than ever with fast changes in the society including the violent spread of COVID-19 pandemic” (p. 4). Wieland & Kollias (2020) study on online learning before, during and after COVID-19 indicates that during COVID-19 people are pushed to online platform overnight especially in teaching learning phenomena and the author predicts that after COVID-19 we will experience refinement in the way of teaching and engaging students as a result of our settlement in new normal. When face-to-face classes will resume there will be a dramatic shift in setting up safeguards to ensure only online mode any time and keep the best practices that already have achieved. Thus the necessity and use of smartphone will persist.

6. Strategic directions to achieve success for mobile phone industry

6.1. Approach for responding to external market

Porter (1979), the professor of Harvard business school introduced five competitive forces model widely known as Porter's five competitive forces model. According to him, the idea of developing strategy is to sustain in competition. Intense competition is not an unusual thing, rather it is a common problem for industry. Due to COVID-19 pandemic situation in current time, the pattern of competition in mobile phone industry has increased many-fold and companies need to adopt strategy to sustain and achieve success. The Porter's five forces model is used as a framework for assessing and evaluating competitive position of a company. Hence it is recommended for industry participant to follow the widely accepted model as this model is very much important for mobile phone companies to strengthen their market position. The five forces as suggested by Porter (1976) is discussed below in light of global mobile phone industry from strategic point of view:

6.1.1. Potential new entrants

Any time new companies can enter the industry and create threat for existing companies which is known as potential new entrants. These companies is not in industry now but they can choose to enter as they have the capability. Nowadays, we see a lot of emerging mobile phone companies entering the industry with an adding facilities for users. Any time it can happen that a new company expands its business globally with much innovative products with superior quality that can create threat for existing top ranked companies. To deal with this threats existing companies can use the capability of achieving economies of scale, brand loyalty, absolute cost structure. During this uncertain situation, it is hard to predict for potential new entrant as economic condition has been becoming worsen, hence, global mobile phone companies need not so worried regarding this force.

6.1.2. Rivalry among competing sellers

The most challenging task of any company to compete in the industry with existing competitors. Intensity of rivalry is a function of industry competitive structure, demand conditions, cost conditions etc. This challenge results in rivalry among existing industry participants. We see huge competition among the existing industry participants throughout the world to gain market share in this industry. The top rated global mobile phone brands have been successfully operating their businesses likely, Samsung, Huawei, iPhone, Xiaomi, Oppo etc. But exception seen like Nokia, Microsoft, and Motorola could to stand out. As discussed earlier, coronavirus has changed the way of doing business, it also intensifies competitions among existing companies. So, it can be said, there is huge rivalry among existing global mobile

phone companies. Here, to become successful, companies must adopt viable strategy.

6.1.3. Bargaining power of buyers

Industry products can be bought by companies like wholesaler/distributor or customers directly from the manufacturer company. These buyers are most powerful when they are dominant, buyers are little in number or limited demand in response to number of products available in market, and the industry supplying the product is composed of many small companies, industry high dependency on buyers, if buyers buy in large quantities, low switching cost for buyers, available number of supplying companies in the market as well as buyer can threaten the seller to enter the market. In general, global mobile phone brands sell their products through their own outlets and with other independent distributors. In this case, buyer can have relative bargaining power on their business activity. However, the industry needs to please the end-users by providing quality products at the low cost to satisfactory post sale services. This force is very much crucial to consider because customer satisfaction is very much important to retain existing customers and to create new customers. The maximum success of mobile phone brands basically depend on achieving buyers' satisfaction. So, it is recommended for global smartphone phone producers to focus on managing bargaining power of customer and in response, they should enhance their product quality, be more responsive to customer needs, become more efficient and reduce cost.

6.1.4. Bargaining power of suppliers

The parts, materials, components, labor are supplied from the suppliers. Suppliers become powerful when their supplied products are vital for industry where there are very few number of suppliers as well as the industry is not essential buyer for suppliers. Most of the global mobile phone companies produce the required raw material by their own thus the dependency of suppliers is less and suppliers cannot apply bargaining power to the major global mobile phone companies.

6.1.5. Substitute products

When same buyer needs are fulfilled by other industry products are called substitute products. The existence of close substitutes is a strong competitive threat as they limit the price that companies can charge for their product. Other things being equal, companies in the industry have the opportunity to raise prices and earn additional profits (Thompson & Strickland, 2003). Mobile phone industry has the substitute of telephone, computer and internet communication sites and apps. Thus to reduce the risk of substitute products the industry tends to adopt these substitute in their own premise.

6.2. Competitive strategic approaches

The five generic competitive strategies which is an author-expanded version of a three-strategy classification discussed in Porter (1979), competitive strategy. Five distinct competitive strategic approaches suggested by Thompson and Strickland (2003) stand out and it is also recommended for mobile phone companies to adopt any one or many of the following approaches based on the resource strength and market position:

6.2.1. A low-cost provider strategy is striving to achieve lower overall costs than rivals and appealing to a broad spectrum of customers, usually by underpricing

Strategic implication of the global mobile phone industry: Analyzing COVID-19 impact from competitive viewpoint

rivals. For global brands, low-cost strategy is not feasible because this strategy can mislead and revert the customers from purchasing with the notion that cheap product is bad product.

6.2.2. **A broad differentiation strategy** is seeking to differentiate the company's product offering from rivals' in ways that will appeal to a broad spectrum of buyers. This strategy is very suitable for global brands having much customer reliability and trust where they are not price concerned rather focus on product quality and added attributes or features.

6.2.3. **A best-cost provider strategy** is giving customers more value for the money by incorporating good-to-excellent product attributes at a lower cost than rivals; the target is to have the lowest (best) costs in producing the products and offering it at lowest prices in comparison with competitors having comparable values. This strategy is not suitable for premium product producer companies. Rather companies having moderately customer confidence on quality and service who are at the same time price sensitive too.

6.2.4. **A focused (or market niche) strategy based on low costs** is concentrating on a narrow buyer segment and outcompeting rivals by having lower costs than rivals and thus being able to serve niche members at a lower price. This strategy is feasible in markets where niche customer groups are highly price sensitive. Companies having low customer trust in quality and service should target to grab these groups' needs.

6.2.5. **A focused (or market niche) strategy based on differentiation** is focusing on a narrow buyer segment and gain success by competing with rivals through delivering these focused buyers some kind of customized product attributes. Thus the niche customer tastes and needs are fulfilled in better way other than their competitors. This strategy is effective for those companies that produce highly qualitative products and set premium prices for these products.

Each of these five generic competitive approaches stakes out a different market position. Each involves distinctively different approaches to competing and operating the business.

7. Conclusion and future research direction

In this paper, the author tries to show the global mobile phone brands especially smartphones' current market position based on the units sold, revenue earned, profit generated, customer demand etc. Again, the strategic implications during and after the pandemic situation has been discussed. This study is basically designed to realize the impact of COVID-19 on this industry. From the study, we can assume that although in many cases the industry is negatively affected due to pandemic situation but other positive impact of COVID-19 generated from other sectors like education sectors' going online, telecommunications sectors' increased demand for communications, other different sectors' work from home which in consequence create dire need for having a smart device as a mandatory tool accelerate the attractiveness for this industry. This has caused increased demand for global mobile phone brands worldwide despite the reduced purchasing ability of the customers. Again, it is also assumed that the demand for these global brands will be increasing in future that will sustain for long term time period. As a result, the industry will appear as more competitive than earlier time prior to pandemic situation. Consequently, it is more important for global mobile phone brands to be more strategic to outcompete and outperform their rival companies. As we know, the main

competitive weapon along with maintaining the quality, efficiency, innovation where the company needs to focus on its outer environment. To cope up with this environment, following Porter's five competitive forces model rigorously might result in good competitive position. Thus these global brands will be able to sustain in the pandemic time as well as in the new normal situation after the pandemic time. Finally, some other strategic directions are given that can be applied for sustainability and growth.

It can be concluded that with the remarks that our research community can conduct an insightful and a detailed research in this field of global mobile phone industry rigorously showing the actual impact of COVID-19 at the end of pandemic situation completely withdrawn from macro level. In this case the research question can be formulated as what are the real long term impact of COVID-19 on global mobile phone industry? In line with the research question, appropriate strategic direction should be given so that the industry can be benefited for further development. Another important thing that this study omits, the little brand in this industry should be included to visualize the total scenario on COVID-19 impact on this mobile phone industry. The study should focus on collecting primary data from the industry authenticate sources. In-depth interview with industry participants as well as the customers should be conducted. Again, studies can be conducted in micro level too based on a single country or market to show that country's situation of mobile phone industry.

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